

FACTSHEET

ECOSYSTEM SERVICE
ASSESSMENT • FEB 2026

© Makrowilli / WWF

ASSESSING THE IMPACTS OF NATURE CONSERVATION ON ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

MAKING THE BENEFITS OF NATURE CONSERVATION VISIBLE

The broader societal benefits of nature conservation projects, extending far beyond biodiversity alone, are often largely unrecognized. We believe that these benefits, direct and indirect contributions of ecosystems to human well-being, should be brought to the forefront.

STRAIGHTFORWARD APPROACH TO INTEGRATE ECOSYSTEM SERVICES INTO PROJECT ASSESSMENT

We suggest a method which is simple, ensures comparability based on existing standards and can be quickly implemented.

We mapped the official classifications of **CICES Ecosystem Service Groups** with so-called **logic chains**, based on the concept of SEEA-EA (System of Environmental-Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting) (United Nations, 2021).

This results in a questionnaire for assessing the impact of nature conservation projects on ecosystem services (next page).

Classification - a “unifying language”

To assess the impact of nature conservation projects on ecosystem services, a methodology based on established systems has great added value.. Ecosystem service classifications improve communication by increasing clarity and consistency in terms.

CICES – Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services - was developed by the European Environment Agency. It is one of only a few systems that follows the rules of classification science: completeness, mutually exclusiveness, consistency and relevance (Finisdore et al., 2020).

Official CICES Classifications can be accessed at <https://cices.eu/>

Literature

- Finisdore, J., Rhodes, C., Haines-Young, R., Maynard, S., Wielgus, J., Dvorskas, A., Houdet, J., Quétier, F., Lamothe, K. A., Ding, H., Soullard, F., Van Houtven, G., & Rowcroft, P. (2020). The 18 benefits of using ecosystem services classification systems. *Ecosystem Services*, 45, 101160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101160>
- United Nations, 2021. Ecosystem Services Logic Chains. System of Environmental Economic Accounting – Ecosystem Accounting. Available at: <https://seea.un.org/ecosystem-accounting>

For each “CICES Group”, the logic chain describes various characteristics that can help clarify different aspects of the ecosystem services, which leads to a common understanding and a uniform assessment across individual projects.

Example of a logic chain for CICES Group 2.1.1. The CICES Classification can be accessed at cices.eu. SEEA-EA Logic Chains can be mapped to CICES groups using the Reference List Crosswalk (seea.un.org/ecosystem-accounting)

CICES Group	Reduction of nutrient loads and mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes
Common ecosystem type/s	Many ecosystem types: forest and woodland (air filtration), freshwater ecosystems and associated vegetation (water purification)
Ecological factors determining supply	Ecosystem type and condition (e.g., vegetation, micro-organisms), chemical state (e.g., pollutant concentrations)
Societal factors determining supply	Ecosystem management; location type and volume of released pollutants
Factors determining use	People, buildings affected by pollution
Potential physical metric(s)	Tonnes of pollutants absorbed or remediated
Benefits	Reduced concentrations of pollutants providing improved health outcomes, reduced damage to buildings, reduced treatment or disposal costs
Main users and beneficiaries	Households and businesses
Project Impact	

→ The Evaluation of a project's impact

With qualitative estimates based on expert knowledge

Guided by information from the logic chain, the project impact for each ecosystem service is assessed:

- Improved
- Declined
- Remained unchanged
- Not applicable

OPPORTUNITIES AND ADVANTAGES

Integrating ecosystem services into the assessment of nature conservation measures has several benefits:

- + **Holistic View**
Moves beyond benefits for biodiversity and shows added value for nature and people
- + **Communication**
Ecosystem services become visible and their benefits comprehensible
- + **Improving public acceptance and stakeholder support**
Leads to better understanding of the value of nature conservation for society, which in turn increases acceptance and support from the public

Compared to other methods the suggested approach has the following advantages:

- **Minimal Effort:** No complex calculations are required
- **Comparability:** Official classifications are used
- **Communication:** based on straightforward numbers

Results

Provide an immediate count of altered ecosystem services

Example results for one project:

- 17 of 23 CICES ecosystem service groups improved
- 2 of 23 CICES ecosystem service groups declined
- 4 of 23 CICES ecosystem service groups remained unchanged
- 1 of 23 CICES ecosystem service groups is not applicable

Example results for a summarized assessment of several projects:

